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In- Silico Characterization of Antidiabetic DPP-IV Inhibitors from *Tinospora crispa*

Maya*

Abstract

Human dipeptidyl peptidase-IV (DPP-IV) inhibitors have become a potential class of oral antidiabetic drugs in the search for efficient treatment approaches for diabetes mellitus (DM). Many current drugs have side effects despite their promise, which emphasizes the need for new and safer substitutes. Treatment for type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) frequently depends on incretin hormones (GLP-1 and GIP), which are essential for metabolism because they encourage the secretion of insulin, among other functions. These incretins are deactivated by the DPP-IV enzyme, hence finding powerful DPP-IV inhibitors as possible antidiabetic medications is necessary. Despite its availability, synthetic inhibitors such as vildagliptin, sitagliptin, and saxagliptin may have negative side effects. On the other hand, a number of natural medicines and plants inhibit the DPP-IV enzyme, providing safer and more efficient substitutes for the treatment of diabetes. This study employs a multi-faceted approach, in-silico molecular docking, to investigate the antidiabetic potential of phytoconstituents derived from *Tinospora crispa* as potential DPP-IV inhibitors. Molecular docking analysis of 13 phytoconstituents from *T. crispa* reveals that twelve exhibit superior binding affinity ($\Delta G \geq -7.0$ kcal/mol) and remarkably low inhibition constants ($K_i \leq 5.27$ μ M) compared to the established drug vildagliptin ($\Delta G = -7.0$ kcal/mol, $K_i = 7.39$ μ M). Among the all compounds, Borapetol B, borapetol a, n-cis-Feruloyltyramine, Moupinamide, Sterol and Clionasterol confirms their drug-likeness properties. These compounds adhere to Lipinski's Rule of Five, demonstrating favourable drug-like characteristics. The findings suggest that naturally derived phytochemicals from *T. crispa*, hold promise as potential DPP-IV inhibitors. These compounds, exhibiting robust in-silico characteristics, merit further experimental validation and may represent safer and more effective candidates for the development of novel antidiabetic agents.

Keywords: Dipeptidyl Peptidase-IV, Molecular docking, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), *Tinospora crispa*, Antidiabetic agents.

Introduction

Diabetes ranks among the top 10 causes of death, along with cancer, respiratory conditions, and cardiovascular disease (CVD), making it one of the biggest global health emergencies of this century [1]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) were responsible for 74% of fatalities worldwide in 2019. Diabetes was the tenth greatest cause of death worldwide, accounting for 1.6 million deaths. It is estimated that diabetes would claim the lives of approximately 592 million people by 2035 [2]. Weight gain and hypoglycaemia are two unfavourable side effects of these drugs, despite the fact that raising insulin secretion has demonstrated therapeutic benefits for T2DM patients [3]. Therefore, the development of improved drugs to treat type

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2 diabetes is of critical importance. For type 2 diabetes, inhibiting human dipeptidyl peptidase-IV (DPP-IV) has been suggested as a potential treatment strategy [4]. A conserved exopeptidase that regulates proteins, DPP-IV can either float freely in the extracellular space or be attached to the plasma membrane. It affects the immune system, oxidative stress, migration and differentiation, glucose metabolism, and cellular signalling [5]. Inhibiting DPP-IV enhances glucose homeostasis and reduces the risk of hypoglycemia [6]. This has garnered significant interest from the pharmaceutical industry, leading to the development and market introduction of DPP-IV inhibitors such as sitagliptin, saxagliptin, alogliptin, linagliptin, and vildagliptin [7]. However, extensive research indicates that CD26/DPP-IV is also crucial for the immune system, particularly for T cell activation [8]. DPP-IV inhibition is therefore a two-edged sword because synthetic DPP-IV inhibitors may have adverse consequences.

In the current day, the use of medicinal herbs is growing quickly. These natural treatments have demonstrated encouraging results in the treatment of diabetes and its associated problems, with a decreased risk of adverse effects and greater acceptance. Many studies have been conducted on the bioactive substances present in medicinal plants that inhibit DPP-4 activity; coumarins, quercetin, and resveratrol are examples of extremely potent DPP-4 inhibitors with IC₅₀ values in the nanomolar range [9].

Tinospora crispa (*T. crispa*, Menispermaceae), a medicinal plant used to treat DM, was able to cause a reduction in serum glucose level in diabetic rats, and the hypoglycemic effect was probably due to its insulinotropic activity [10]. *T. crispa* also increased peripheral utilization of glucose and inhibited hepatic glucose release [11].

The overall objective of this work is to further the development of new and improved antidiabetic medicines by determining the potential of phytochemicals present in *T. crispa* as DPP-4 inhibitors. In order to analyse and evaluate phytoconstituents produced from *T. crispa* and determine their potential as DPP-4 inhibitors for the treatment of type 2 diabetic mellitus (T2DM), a computational approach was employed in this study.

Materials and Methods

Target Protein Retrieval and Preparation

The protein DPP-4 complexed with the inhibitor Vildagliptin (Pdb id: 6B1E) was obtained in PDB format from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) repository [12]. By opening the PDB file with the BIOVIA Discovery Studio Visualizer [13], the prebound ligand groups, heteroatoms, and water molecules were eliminated, along with any undesired interference from the aforementioned groups, to produce a processed protein structure free of duplicate chains. Ultimately, this processed structure was transformed into pdbqt format by making it into a macromolecule using the PyRx software's built-in Open Babel tool [14].

Ligand Retrieval and Preparation

Thirteen compounds from *T. crispa* (Table 1) obtained by the IMPPAT website (Indian Medicinal Plants, Phytochemistry and Therapeutics) [15] and were retrieved from PubChem Data Bank [16] in 3D .sdf format. Energy minimization and conversion into. pdbqt format of these compounds were done by use of Open Babel software inbuilt in PyRx software.

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Docking Procedure and Analysis of Docked Results

Using the Vina Wizard Control from the PyRx - Virtual Screening Software Tool, the docking operation was started. The Grid box was set to cover all amino acid residues in the receptor protein's active site in Chain A (center at x: 37.2640, y: 51.1697, z: 35.7987, and dimension (in Å) at x: 27.8175, y: 28.9771, z: 25.0000). The Vina Run exhaustiveness was set to value nine, and the procedure was then carried out, showing results in the form of binding affinity (kcal/mol) and root mean square deviation (rmsd) lower and upper bound values. The protein-ligand complexes that had docked best pose (with zero lower and upper rmsd values) were selected for further analysis. The binding sites of the docked complexes were investigated in order to create a 2D and 3D visualization of the ligand-protein interaction for each complex using the BIOVIA Discovery Studio Visualizer software.

Computation of Inhibition Constant

The inhibition constant (K_i value), which is used to assess how effective the interaction is, is predicted by the molecular docking analysis. Predicted binding energies and modifications in hydrogen bonds made with the residues of the protein's active site are also taken into account. The dissociation constant (K_d) is the inhibition constant, also known as the K_i value of the docked enzyme-inhibitor complex. Smaller K_i values are related to higher inhibition and a lower dissociation probability. It is calculated with the formula $K_i = \exp(\Delta G/RT)$, where ΔG is the free energy of binding, R is the gas constant (1.987 Kcal/K/mol), and T is the temperature (298.15 K) [17].

Drug-likeness, Bioavailability Score and Synthetic accessibility Prediction

Pharmacokinetics and Toxicity of candidate molecules decide them to be a drug molecule. In the early stages of Computer Added Drug Design (CADD), Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, and Toxicity (ADMET) of chemicals have been recognized as important considerations. The SwissADME [18] web tools was used to evaluate the Pharmacokinetics, drug-likeness, and medicinal chemistry of these molecules. Important parameters for a drug molecule include pharmacokinetics parameters like P-glycoprotein, HIA (human intestinal absorption), drug-likeness prediction Lipinski, Lipinski Ro5, Pfizer, GSK and Golden Triangle drug rule criteria, and the BBB (Blood-Brain Barrier penetration). In order to evaluate drug-likeness and ascertain whether a compound is likely to be bioactive, a number of additional crucial parameters were employed, including molecular weight, LogP, number of HBA and HBD, as well as the Lipinski, Pfizer, GSK and Golden Triangle guidelines. Most "drug-like" compounds have $\log P \leq 5$, molecular weight (MW) ≤ 500 , number of hydrogen bond acceptors (nHA) ≤ 10 , and number of hydrogen bond donors (nHD) ≤ 5 , according to Lipinski's "Rule of 5" [19].

Results and Discussion

Molecular docking and Molecular interactions (2D and 3D) analysis

Molecular docking and virtual screening, also known as computer-aided drug design (CADD) or rational drug design (RDD), provides a reliable, quick, and affordable method for finding new drugs (lead molecules) and possible druggable protein targets. In this work, we used virtual screening based on molecular docking to identify a potential target for Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Following a comprehensive literature review and considering available crystal structures of proteins pivotal in T2DM's biosynthetic pathways [20], we have selected Dipeptidyl Peptidase-IV (DPP-IV) (Pdb id: 6B1E). This in-silico investigation delved into the likely molecular docking interactions between the selected 13

phytochemicals and the DPP-IV enzyme. The findings were juxtaposed with established T2DM drugs vildagliptin. Out of the 13 compounds, 12 exhibited superior binding energies of -9.3 kcal/mol to -7.2 Kcal/mol compared to the binding energy of drug molecule vildagliptin (-7.0 Kcal/mol) (Table 2). To correlate and examine with the corresponding protein target, the binding affinity (Kcal/mol) of the ligand or inhibitor is a useful metric. Lower binding energies are generally associated with higher ligand affinities, or more negative interactions, with the receptor protein. The ligand that exhibits the highest affinity thus becomes a promising candidate deserving of additional investigation.

Table 2: Binding Affinities, Inhibition constants, Hydrogen Bonding of ligands with Chain A of 6B1E

S. No.	Ligand name	Binding Affinity (ΔG) (kcal/mol)	Inhibition Const. K_i (μM)	No. of H-Bonds	H-Bond Forming Residues	*Other Types of bonds (No. of Other bonds)
1	Sterol	-8.0	1.36	1	Val546	Pi-Sigma (1) Pi-Alkyl (4)
2	Clionasterol	-7.9	1.61	0	---	Pi-Sigma (1) Pi-Alkyl (1)
3	Tinocrisposide	-8.1	1.15	6	Glu205, Glu206, Tyr547 Lys554, Ser630, Tyr662	Pi-Pi T-Shaped (2), Pi-Alkyl (1)
4	borapetoside D	-9.3	0.15	10	Arg125, Glu206, Arg368, Tyr547, Trp629, Tyr662, Arg669	Pi-Donor (1), Pi-Pi T-shaped (1), C-H bond (3)
5	Borapetoside E	-8.5	0.59	6	Arg125, Arg358, Tyr547, Ser630, Tyr662, Arg669	Pi-Pi T-shaped (1), Pi-Donor (1), C-H (1)
6	borapetoside f	-8.0	1.36	8	Glu206, Ser209, Tyr547, Gln553, Ser630, Tyr662	C-H (1), Pi-Alkyl (1)
7	Borapetol B	-7.7	2.27	3	Arg125, Ser209, Tyr547	Pi-Pi Stacked (1), Pi-Sigma (1), Pi-Pi Stacked (1), C-H (2)
8	borapetol a	-8.4	0.69	3	Ser209, Tyr547, Ser630, Tyr662	Pi-Pi Shaped (1), Pi-Donor (1), Unfav. Acc-Acc (1)
9	borapetoside a	-8.3	0.82	3	Ser209, Tyr547	Pi-Donor (2), C-H (4), -Pi Stacked (2), Pi-Anion (1)
10	borapetoside b	-8.0	1.36	4	Glu205, Gln553, Lys554	Unfav. Donor (1)
11	Cordifolide A	-8.0	1.36	6	Glu205, Ser209, Tyr547, Tyr585, Ser630, Tyr662	C-H (1), Pi-Donor (2), Pi-Pi Stacked (1), Pi-Pi T shaped (1) Unfav. Donor-Donor (1)
12	n-cis-Feruloyltyramine	-6.8	10.35	3	Arg125, Tyr547, Asn710	Pi-Pi Stacked (1), C-H (1)
13	Moupinamide	-7.2	5.27	4	Ser209, Arg358, Tyr547	Pi-Pi- Stacked (2), Unfav. Donor - Donor (2)
14	Vildagliptin (control drug)	-7.0	7.39	4	Arg125, Glu206, Ser209, Tyr547	Pi-Alkyl (2), Alkyl (1)

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About thirteen compounds derived from *T. crispa* screened against A chain of 6B1E were selected for post docking analysis. From the multiple screening analysis the DPP-IV binding site exhibits high druggability, meaning that small molecules possessing physicochemical properties similar to those of drugs can be used to achieve precise and tight binding to the enzyme [21-22]. The various interaction motifs that DPP-IV ligands employ include Ser630 (which, along with Asp708 and His740, forms the catalytic triad of the enzyme), the hydrophobic S1 pocket (formed by Tyr631, Val656, Trp659, Tyr662, Tyr666, and Val711), the hydrophobic S2 pocket (formed by Arg125, Phe357, Arg358, Tyr547, Pro550, and Asn710), and the N-terminal recognition region (formed by Glu205, Glu206, and Tyr662) [21-24]. Co-crystalized structure of DPP-4 enzyme with vildagliptin (6B1E) exhibits Hydrogen bonding with residues Arg125, Glu205, Tyr547, Tyr631, Tyr662 and Asn710 and Hydrophobic interactions with residues Phe357, Val656, Tyr662, Tyr666 and Val711 [25]. Interestingly, in this docking investigation vildagliptin forms Hydrogen bonds with residues Glu205 and Arg358 along with Hydrophobic interactions with residues Arg356, Phe357 and Arg358, confirming validity of this docking experiment.

Compound borapetoside D having highest binding affinity (-9.3 Kcal/mol and inhibition constant 0.15 μ M), forms Ten Hydrogen bonds with residues Arg125, Glu206, Arg368, Tyr547, Trp629, Tyr662 and Arg669. Besides these it also showed one Pi-Donor, one Pi-Pi T-shaped bond and three Carbon-Hydrogen bonds which stabilizes the complex and provides highest binding affinity to the complex (Table 2, Fig 4a and 4b). Borapetoside E having binding affinity (-8.5 Kcal/mol and inhibition constant 0.59 μ M) formed Six Hydrogen bonds with residues Arg125, Arg358, Tyr547, Ser630, Tyr662 and Arg669, one Pi-Pi T-shaped, one Pi-Donor and one Carbon-Hydrogen bonds were also formed (Table 2, Fig 5a and 5b). All other remaining ligands also have significant binding affinity with active site residues and binding patterns resembling with control drug molecule vildagliptin (Table 2 and remaining figures).

Fig. 1a*

Fig. 1b**

Sterol

Fig. 2a

Fig. 2b

Clionasterol

Fig. 3a

Tinocrisposide

Fig. 3b

Fig. 4a

borapetoside D

Fig. 4b

Fig. 5a

Borapetoside E

Fig. 5b

Fig. 6a

borapetoside f

Fig. 6b

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Fig. 7a

Borapetol B

Fig. 7b

Fig. 8a

borapetol a

Fig. 8b

Fig. 9a

borapetoside a

Fig. 9b

Fig. 10a

borapetoside b

Fig. 10b

Fig. 1 (a, b) – Fig. 14 (a, b): Showing 14 phytochemicals and drug molecule (in Table 1, S. No. 1-14) docked with human DPP-IV enzyme (chain A of 6B1E). (a) The 3D image showing significant interactions with donor and acceptor H –bonds regions (b) The molecular level interactions of the molecules are depicted in the 2D plot.

Drug-likeness, Bioavailability Score and Synthetic accessibility of ligands

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On the basis of Physico-chemical and Molecular properties of ligands and drug molecule, Drug-likeness, Bioavailability Score and Synthetic accessibility of ligands are presented in Table 3. Drug-likeness prediction, Lipinski Rule (Ro5) is valid for Borapetol B, borapetol a, n-cis-Feruloyltyramine, Moupinamide and Vildagliptin (control drug) with 0 violation. Maximum bioavailability Score (0.55) is found to be compounds which obey Lipinski Rule (Ro5). Synthetic accessibility is maximum (8.18) for borapetoside D molecule (Table 3).

Table 3: Drug-likeness, Bioavailability Score and Synthetic accessibility of ligands

S. No.	Ligand name	Lipinski Rule (Ro5)	Bioavailability Score	*Synthetic accessibility
1	Sterol	Yes; 1 violation	0.55	3.76
2	Clionasterol	Yes; 1 violation	0.55	6.30
3	Tinocrisposide	No; 2 violations	0.17	6.61
4	borapetoside D	No; 3 violations	0.17	8.18
5	Borapetoside E	No; 2 violations	0.17	7.07
6	borapetoside f	No; 2 violations	0.17	6.58
7	Borapetol B	Yes; 0 violation	0.55	5.44
8	borapetol a	Yes; 0 violation	0.55	5.23
9	borapetoside a	No; 2 violations	0.17	6.49
10	borapetoside b	No; 2 violations	0.17	6.74
11	Cordifolide A	No; 2 violations	0.17	6.97
12	n-cis-Feruloyltyramine	Yes; 0 violation	0.55	2.55
13	Moupinamide	Yes; 0 violation	0.55	2.55
14	Vildagliptin (control drug)	Yes; 0 violation	0.55	4.76

*from 1 (very easy) to 10 (very difficult)

Conclusions:

Given the global threat posed by diabetes mellitus and the side effects associated with current diabetes medications, the investigation of low-toxicity phytoconstituents represents a promising research direction. This study focused on screening of 13 phytochemicals derived from the *T. crispa* plant, specifically targeting Dipeptidyl Peptidase-IV (DPP-IV) enzymes. These enzymes are oral anti-hyperglycemic agents that inhibit the inactivation of the incretin hormones GLP-1 and GIP, thereby affecting glucose regulation through multiple pathways, including enhanced glucose-dependent insulin secretion, delayed gastric emptying, and reduced postprandial glucagon levels and food intake. Molecular docking analyses identified twelve phytochemicals that exhibited superior binding affinity to the target protein (PDB ID: 6b1e) compared to the conventional DPP-IV inhibitor vildagliptin. On the basis of Physico-chemical and Molecular properties of ligands and drug molecule, drug-likeness, bioavailability score and synthetic accessibility of ligands Borapetol B, borapetol a, n-cis-Feruloyltyramine, Moupinamide, Sterol and Clionasterol confirmed their drug-like properties. These findings suggest that phytochemicals derived from *T. crispa* have the potential to be developed into more effective and safer antidiabetic medications. The next critical step involves subjecting these phytoconstituents to rigorous clinical trials to validate their therapeutic potential and facilitate their incorporation into standard diabetes treatment protocols. The future holds significant promise for leveraging these natural compounds to address the global health challenge of diabetes mellitus.

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